

Strategy Implementation Practices and Performance of Deposit Taking Savings and Credit Cooperatives in Kiambu County, Kenya

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Abstract: The purpose of the study was to determine the influence of communication on performance of Deposit Taking Savings and Credit Cooperatives in the county government of Kiambu. The study adopted following theories, stakeholder, resource-based theory and institutional theory. Targeting 98 Sacco officials in the Kiambu county government, the study employed a descriptive research approach. The study used data from the entire population, which is a census, because the target population is small. A structured questionnaire used to collect data. Data from both primary and secondary sources will be gathered. The questionnaires that have been correctly filled out will be dropped off by the researcher and picked up. Piloting was carried out to evaluate the accuracy and dependability of the data collection tool. Data was arranged, coded, and modified to provide context. Statistics must be used, both descriptive and inferential. To assess whether there is a significant difference between two variables, multiple regression was used. From the findings, organisational structure, organisational culture, resource allocation, and strategic communication were found to be significant effect on performance of Saccos in the county government of Kiambu. The study came up with the following recommendations; the SACCOS management should put into consideration effective communication as it plays an important role in determining whether an organization succeeds or not and that most of the respondents were in agreement with it. Communication is deeply connected with strategic consensus and everybody in the organization must know the direction the organization is going and what are the objectives as well they must know the vision, thus the ideal state. The vision of the county should be well communicated to the staffs of the organization in either formal an informal forms of communication in strategy implementation.

Keywords: Strategy Communication, Strategy Implementation, Performance of SACCOS.

1. INTRODUCTION

The business of the twenty first century irrespective of its size is going to be part of the global business community affecting and being affected by social change, events and pressures from around the world. This is true because of how quickly things are changing and how volatile, discontinuous, and competitive the business environment is. The interaction between business and society has undergone a significant transformation over this time. The globalization of commerce, the growth in the size and power of corporate organizations, the repositioning of the government, and the increasing strategic value of stakeholder connections, knowledge, and brand reputation have been the main forces behind this transition (Olanipekun, 2014). Sacco's who have continuously carried out their strategy have not failed. Failure to implement strategy in any organization continues to be a major issue for many businesses. Firm performance is a multifaceted concept that can include financial performance indicators like profits, market based indicators like market shares, returns of the

shareholders and the added economic value (Sengendo, 2016). Performance can be seen in the overall membership & total deposits, branch network, new products launched to the market, and outreach performance of the SACCOs strategy in the context of Savings and Credit Cooperative Societies (SACCOs). Performance is thus a crucial idea in the context of SACCOs that supports the foundation for these organizations' basic existence. The SACCO movement began in Germany in 1849 and spread throughout Europe, North America, and the rest of the world. The World Council of Credit Unions (WOCCU) was founded in 1970 as a result of the success of SACCOs around the world. Conceptually, WOCCU plays a critical role in enhancing SACCO performance in the world (WOCCU, 2018).

A European business review revealed that, many European firms have been faced with increasing uncertainty and complexity over few years and the chief strategic officer has had little known about its role in contributing to curbing the challenges (Markus, 2013). According to Allio (2015), the White Paper of Strategy Implementation of Chinese Corporations (2014) survey results show that integrating individual contributions to accomplish a common goal has made strategy implementation more crucial than ever. The manager's responsibility is to make sure that internal coordination exists across all organizational components so that the organization may accomplish its objectives. To create a successful and efficient organization that performs in accordance with acceptable standards, it is up to the manager to select the management strategy that suits him or her. Strategy implementation is a crucial and important process in strategic management. Organizations must successfully implement their plans in order to improve performance if they are to succeed (Carter & Pucko, 2010). SACCO performance in Africa began in Ghana in 1959, then spread to countries in the west of the continent including Nigeria and the east African nations of Uganda, Tanzania, and Kenya. The 1960s saw the performance of SACCOs in the African nations that were not British colonies, whereas the 1970s saw exponential growth. The African Confederation of Co-Operative Savings and Credit Associations (ACCOSCA) was founded in 1968 as a result of SACCOs' broad success in Africa. The main goal of ACCOSCA is to improve SACCO performance across the continent of Africa (ACCOSCA, 2018).

Strategy implementation delineates the activities through which organizations define its domain(s) of action and determine how it will navigate or compete within its chosen domain(s) (Murgor, 2014). The dynamic process of adapting to environmental change and the unpredictability of maintaining an effective alignment with the environment while managing internal interdependencies is incredibly difficult for the majority of businesses, involving a wide range of decisions and actions at various organizational levels. Implementing strategies is a sort of organizational adaptation that ensures ongoing organizational effectiveness (Hill & Hoskisson, 2010). Organisations come up with very good strategies to make improvement in the interest of the organisations but never see the light in implementation. In a study conducted by one of the non-governmental organisations the research analysed that although strategy formulation is a hard task for management team, making the strategy work proved to be even more difficult. This is so because implementing strategies is considered to be more of an art than a science, and its research history has been characterized as fragmented. They discovered that when the superior tactics were not successfully used, they did not result in the best performance. This was caused by policy restrictions, managerial skills, and resource allocation, which were cited as the three most important elements affecting the successful execution of a strategy (Omondi, P., Ombui, and Mungatu, 2013).

Atkinson stated that more than half of the strategies that have been devised by organisations are never implemented. She further claims that this is due to increase in competition and globalisation. She emphasises that this makes it more important to have effective strategy implementation (Atkinson, 2006). In his research, Allio concurs that plans fail during the implementation stage and emphasizes the fact that managers can close the gap between rhetoric and reality by employing an approach, format, and procedure that are simple and straightforward (Allio, 2005). Robin Speculand claims that nine out of ten strategies fail at the implementation phase. He further explains that this is because after leaders are left to implement the strategy, they have to figure out how to let the people know of the changes, what and why we need this change. He states that "implementation is not a single decision or action but a cluster of structured and sustained activities over a period of time" (Speculand, 2009).

The SACCO movement in Kenya is the largest in Africa as a continent with a total asset to gross domestic product (GDP) standing at 5.7% compared to 3% and 0.7% for Rwanda and Ethiopia respectively (SASRA, 2020). Given the low interest rate that Kenyan SACCOs charge on loans and advances compared to other financial institutions, one would expect an exponential performance in uptake of credit facilities from these institutions. However, this has not been the case as evidenced by 11.99% and 11.27% minimal performance in deposits for 2018 and 2019 respectively (SASRA, 2020).

Literature has shown that successful implementation of strategies can help the firm to realize outstanding performance and thus performance (Nkuru, 2015; Muendo & Ogutu, 2020). According to Donna and Wanjira (2018), performance and thus performance of the firm require successful implementation of the formulated strategies. Similarly, Wangeci (2017) shared that performance of the firm requires implementation of the strategies that have been established after strategic planning. Odhiambo (2016) indicates that strategy implementation entails identification of measurable and mutually determining annual objectives which convert long-term objectives into specific and short-term goals. It also includes the development of specific functional strategies which translate grand strategies at business level into current action plans for sub units of the company. Thus execution must be controlled and evaluated if the strategy is to be successfully implemented and adjusted to changing conditions. However, during implementation, various challenges are encountered and need to be addressed if the strategy is to be realized. According to Kihara, Bwisa and Kihoro (2016) the strategy implementation process determines whether an organization excels, survives or dies depending on the manner in which it is undertaken by the stakeholders. Strategy implementation process involves placing objectives, strategies, and policies into action through the development of programs, budgets, and procedures. Strategy formulation precedes implementation making implementation a key part of strategic management.

Implementation of strategies requires the firm to critically examine the structure, resources and culture so as to realize superior performance that may promote performance (Mailu, Ntale & Nguui, 2018). An organizational structure would provide the duties and responsibilities of the staff while reinforcing the existing channels of communication during strategy implementation (Mailu et al., 2018). An organization's structure is made up of formally established systems and structures like departments, procedures and policies that an organization has put in place (Siapei, 2015). According to the SACCO Societies Regulatory Authority, between 2010 and 2017 there were 14 deposit taking SACCOs registered and operating in Kiambu County, Kenya (SASRA, 2020). SACCOs have gained popularity in rural areas like Kiambu because they give access to financial services, which connects households to a wider economic world. SACCOs today more than ever need to properly implement strategies that spur performance and competitive grounds in addition to sustainable performance due to the rising demand for the services that SACCOs offer. This is the current study's primary area of interest.

In the financial year 2017/18 and 2018/19, the performance in total assets stood at 11.98% and 12.45%, deposits grow at a rate of 11.99% and 11.27% while gross loans grew by 13.01% and 12.09% respectively (SASRA, 2020). This trend implies that the performance rate of deposits was less than that of the assets and that the rate of performance in gross loans exceeded the performance rate of total deposits of the deposit taking SACCOs in the County of Kiambu. This further suggests that the aggregate rate of demand for loans and advances by members of these SACCOs is far above the rate at which these institutions are able to mobilize and grow deposits and savings from members. There was performance in dormant members of these SACCOs by 40.1% in 2019 from 482,526 to 676,052 as of 2018 (SASRA, 2020). There has been minimal performance in the share of the assets of these institutions against GDP at 5.44%, 5.55% and 5.72% for the periods 2017, 2018 and 2019 respectively (SASRA, 2020). The environments in which SACCOs operate have become increasingly uncertain posing a lot of challenges. It is clear that lack of appropriate understanding of the process of strategy implementation has caused many organizations to endure SACCO performance delays. Everyone working for the company must be aware of the goals and methods the SACCOs will use while formulating and implementing their strategies (Taneja, Sewell, & Odom, 2015).

For many SACCOs in Kenya, one of the main challenges has been Performance (Ndung'u & Mutinda, 2022). SACCOs in Kenya have recently had to contend with increased competition from banks and other financial organizations, as well as dangers like the development of new mergers from existing local and foreign financial firms. New government rules, particularly those pertaining to product prices, have also been implemented, and they are not favorable to the SACCOs' much-needed performance in the nation (Mugo, Waitthaka, & Muathe, 2017). The minimum SACCO performance target as per most Counties in Kenya is at 10%, however, the current performance rates of most SACCOs average at about 5%, which is lower than the prescribed minimum (Boen, 2015). This signifies slow performance of the SACCOs in Kenya. Performance in dormant membership of the SACCOs in Kenya was at 40.1% in 2018, the performance rate of gross loans compared to deposits and performance in NPLs was at 6.14%, 6.30% and 6.15% in the periods 2017, 2018 and 2019 respectively (SASRA, 2020). These point to a potential and impending crisis that could make many Kenyan SACCOs unsustainable. These SACCOs' failure would have disastrous ramifications for the following reasons: First, according to Wakaro (2020), these SACCOs provide a direct or indirect source of income for around 63% of Kenyans. Secondly, these SACCOs control about Kshs. 500 billion in form of savings and assets in the economy with the contribution of assets top

GDP standing at 5.44%, 5.55% and 5.72% for 2017, 2018 and 2019 respectively (SASRA, 2020). Lastly, of the overall savings mobilized and loans advanced by SACCOs in Africa, SACCOs in Kenya contribute 62% and 65% of the savings and total loans respectively and thus a powerful movement in Africa (Wakaro, 2020). Nkuru (2015) argues that in order to achieve performance, SACCOs in Kenya should put good tactics into practice. According to the literature now in use, implementing a strategy is a challenging phase with a high failure rate that could affect the firm's performance.

Muendo and Ogutu (2020) contend that just 14% of the firms have been effective in putting their plans into practice, despite the fact that around 80% of them have well-formulated strategies. According to Nwachukwu et al. (2019), who studied the performance of telecommunications companies in Nigeria, a primary focus should be placed on the factors that influence how these companies implement their strategies in order to assure the success of the businesses. In their investigations, Donna and Wanjira (2018) and Wangeci (2017) concentrated on how company strategies were implemented and how performance was impacted; as a result, the idea of firm performance was not investigated in either study. The research described above highlight the notion that strategy implementation is essential for performance, but they stop short of extending this relationship to company performance. The relationship between strategy execution and performance, particularly in the SACCO sub-sector, has not been studied. Other studies were conducted in different contexts like pharmaceutical manufacturing firms and not specifically the SACCOs. There are some studies that were done in other countries like Nigeria and not Kenya while other studies covered dependent variables like performance and not firm performance. Implementation entails putting strategies into actions, and it is achieved through appropriate financial budgeting, and planning among others (Wheelen & Hunger, 2008; Chankseliani, Qoraboyev & Gimranova, 2021). Most organization usually fail to achieve their targets because there is often improper implementation or no implementation at all (Bigler, 2011). According to Kiplagat (2014), approximately 80% of the global organization's reports to have great strategies. However, research report shows that only about 33% implement their strategic plans accurately. Other investigations like Wangeci (2017) adopted a case study design where Nairobi Water and Sewerage Company was studied thus presenting a methodological gap. Thus, in the efforts of bridging the gaps highlighted as above, the study that aimed at underpinning the effect of strategic communication on performance of deposit taking SACCOS in Kiambu County.

2. STRATEGY COMMUNICATION

According to Niclas (2014), the business context of organizations is an ever-changing environment. Whether an organization succeeds or fails is significantly influenced by communication. (Miriti 2013). Consensus on strategic matters is closely related to communication. Everyone in the organization needs to be aware of the goals and the direction it is taking. They must also be aware of the vision, or the ideal situation. This consensus is reached through communication. It is the responsibility of management to make sure that there is communication among themselves, middle management, various organizational functions, and other key links. In order to achieve common views, attitudes, and beliefs across the workforce and eventually advance the organization's performance, Rapert et al. (2002) perceive the necessity for regular communication as well as vertical communication throughout the organization.

Effective Communication and Organizational Performance Communication is an essential tool in an organization by facilitating coordination and teamwork amongst the various players (Kimotho & Mwasiaji, 2019). As a result, it is a key component of information interchange within the context of the organization and a crucial tool for the operation of the organization internally. An organization's performance level is frequently influenced by how well it communicates. The complete process of adopting strategy cannot occur to the levels initially expected without effective and appropriate communication methods and structures (Baini & Mwasiaji, 2018). The effectiveness of communication is determined by an understanding of how different organizational stakeholders interact. Procedure documentation and internal communication channels are examples of effective communication strategies. Olang (2015) argues that documenting internal communication channels and procedures, which are an essential instrument in the process of implementing a strategy, is a fundamental component for effective communication. Understanding these processes and channels is crucial, but that is not all that is required; it is also crucial to reinforce them and make sure that staff are aware of the goals and mission. By examining and updating areas that have issues, communication can be used to forecast an organization's future and help it maintain funding and sustainability. Strategy implementation and communication work hand in hand by promoting the widespread understanding of the organization. This happens both externally and internally (Ayusa, 2016). Olang (2015) describes strategic communication as including communication as part of the strategy implementation

process. Shimizu (2017) has the view that the Chief Executive Officer (CEO) has a responsibility of relaying the organization's vision and provide a guide in the strategic planning course. It is vital to involve the entire team in the strategy implementation report because it increases motivation and increases the shared vision of the organization of achieving strategic goals (Kimotho & Mwasijaji, 2019). Clarity and consistency in the strategy's communication, implementation, and evaluation are necessary to meet these strategic goals. Communication that is precise and reliable helps to establish strong bonds. Lack of coordination caused by poor communication prevents businesses from accomplishing their aims and ambitions. Having frequent training on the value of communication would help organizations become more professional in their communication.

At Nnamdi Azikiwe University in Awka, Ngozi and Ifeoma (2015) concentrated on the impact of effective communication on organizational performance. The academic and non-academic staff served as the population for this study. 130 academic staff members and 170 non-academic staff members made up the population. Utilizing stratified random sampling and the Taro Yamane approach, 166 samples were selected. The hypotheses were analyzed using chi-square. The study's conclusions demonstrated that good communication is the key to improving employees' ability to run a company effectively and efficiently. The study suggested that every firm make an effort to incorporate effective communication as a crucial component of its management strategies.

Shonubi and Akintaro (2016) conducted a study to look at how good communication affects organizational performance. A number of empirical research on communication and organizational performance served as the foundation for the discussion. If management adopts the following suggestions, there may still be opportunity for improvement and better performance as a result: more conceptual clarity prior to communicating; improved comprehension of the physical and societal context when talking; a detailed examination of communication's goal; Top-down and bottom-up consultation should be used in planning communications, and all information should be made both implicit and explicit.

Wang (2011) examined the relationship between social-emotional-oriented communication, work-oriented communication, and organizational commitment in China in order to better understand how communication might increase employees' organizational commitment. The study used statistics to analyse the information gathered via surveys. A total of 69 personnel from a local government agency in China took part in the study. The results of regression analyses showed that work-oriented communication is a strong positive predictor of affective commitment and normative commitment, and that social-emotional communication between superiors and subordinates is a positive predictor of affective commitment, as well as the perceived amount of organizational strategic information and vertical interaction with management.

A study was conducted by Udegbe, Udegbe, Ogundipe, Ganiyat and Rashdidat (2012) to establish the impact of business communication on organizational performance in Nigerian companies. Using the survey method, the study obtained sample data from 100 small and large manufacturing and service companies operating in Lagos State of Nigeria. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, percentages and t-test analysis. The study found that effective business communication is emphasized to a reasonable extent in the surveyed Nigerian companies. However, the level of emphasize is a question of degree. It was also found that the extent of practices of effective business communication, were related to the category of business (service versus manufacturing) and its size.

In a study published in 2015, Otieno, Waiganjo, and Njeru examined the impact of employee communication on organizational performance in Kenya's horticultural sector. The 14 flower farms in Kenya that are located in Naivasha made up the population of this study. The study's target audience was the farms' employees. The study employed a cross-sectional survey research design. The respondents to the study were sampled using the stratified sampling approach. With a Pearson correlation value of 0.466 at a level of significance of 0.000, the findings of the correlation study demonstrated that employee communication is statistically significant. The study came to the conclusion that one of the key factors influencing an organization's effectiveness in Kenya's horticultural industry is employee communication.

Since successful strategy execution is concerned with an organization's entire productivity in terms of stock turnover, customers, profitability, and market share, the organizations will be able to accomplish their objectives in an efficient way and with competitiveness. Given generating profits is a fundamental goal of businesses, the concept of organizational performance is essential to them. According to Iravo et al. (2013), a study on the factors that affect organizational performance was driven by the question of why some businesses succeed while others fail. Concerned with an organization's overall productivity in terms of stock turnover, clients, profitability, and market share is organizational performance.

Because generating profits is a fundamental goal of businesses, the concept of organizational performance is essential to them. According to Iravo et al. (2013), one of the key issues in business has been why some businesses prosper while others fail, and this has inspired research on the drivers of organizational performance. According to Fwaya (2006), performance is a formula for evaluating how well an organization is operating under specific conditions, such as productivity, employee morale, and effectiveness.

According to Nzube and Nyaega (2012), strategic management is centered on performance management and improvement because most of it is concerned with defining and measuring performance. According to Awino (2011), a company needs to generate high returns and identify performance drivers at all levels of the business in order to be successful. The goal approach, which asserts that an organization pursues specific, measurable goals, is one of the three approaches to performance in an organization that Odhiambo (2009) identified. According to this method, performance is measured by how well these objectives were achieved. The second strategy is the systems resource strategy, which characterizes performance as the interaction between a company's environment and itself. This idea gauges an organization's performance by how well it can protect the environment's scarce and priceless resources. The process view is the third strategy, and it defines performance in terms of how an organization's human resource behaves in an organization (Waiganjo et al., 2012). Performance is highlighted by Kiragu (2005) from four angles: financial, customer, internal procedures, and innovativeness. According to Odhuno and Wadongo (2010), the financial perspective highlights the profit margin, asset turnover, leverage, cash flow, and working capital as the major financial drivers of improving performance.

According to Fwaya (2006), performance is a formula for evaluating how well an organization is operating under specific conditions, such as productivity, employee morale, and effectiveness. According to Nzube and Nyaega (2012), strategic management is centered on performance management and improvement because much strategic thinking revolves around defining and quantifying performance. According to Awino (2011), a company must record high returns and identify performance drivers from the top to the bottom of the organization in order to be successful. According to Odhiambo (2009), the first approach evaluates performance in terms of achieving these objectives. The second strategy is the systems resource strategy, which characterizes performance as the interaction between a company's environment and itself. This idea gauges an organization's performance by how well it can protect the environment's scarce and priceless resources. The process viewpoint is the third strategy, and it defines performance in terms of how an organization's human resources behave (Waiganjo et al., 2012).

Performance is highlighted by Kiragu (2005) from four angles: financial, customer, internal procedures, and innovativeness. According to Odhuno and Wadongo (2010), the financial perspective highlights the profit margin, asset turnover, leverage, cash flow, and working capital as the main financial drivers of improving performance. In terms of brand image, customer satisfaction, customer retention, and customer profitability, the customer focus explains performance. Internal processes are concerned with the effectiveness of every system within the company, whereas innovativeness is focused on how quickly a company can adjust to new circumstances.

3. METHOD

This study adopted a descriptive research design. The target population for the study was comprised of 98 SACCOs managers in Kiambu County, Kenya. Given the study's small sample size, the study utilized all of the population's census data. Data collection instrument was questionnaires. Piloting was done to test the validity and reliability of the data collection instrument. Once data is collected, it was crosschecked and verified for errors, completeness, and consistency. It was then be coded, entered and analysed descriptively using IBM Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS 23). Pearson correlation analysis was used to test the relationship between variables in the study hypotheses. ANOVA multiple linear regression analysis were adopted computed to determine the statistical relationship between the independent variable and the dependent.

4. DISCUSSION

The objective of the study is to effect of strategic communication on performance of SACCOS in deposits in Kiambu County. The results of the descriptive statistics of strategic communication on performance of SACCOS in deposits in Kiambu County are shown in Table 4.1(a) According to the results, 86.4% of the respondents either agreed or strongly agreed that communication plays an important role in determining whether an organization succeeds or not. This statement had a mean score of 4.4407 indicating that most of the respondents were in agreement with it. Additionally, 53.4% of the

respondents either agreed or strongly agreed, while 23.7% were uncertain regarding communication is deeply connected with strategic consensus and everybody in the organization must know the direction the organization is going and what are the objectives as well they must know the vision, thus the ideal state. This indicated a moderate level of affirmation by the respondents which was supported by the mean score of 3.5169.

Further, 83.1% of the respondents either agreed or strongly agreed that the vision of the county is well communicated to the staffs of the organization. This statement had a mean score of 4.3305 indicating that the majority of the respondent agreed with it. Also, 56.8% of the respondents either agreed or strongly agreed that the firm both the formal and informal forms of communication in strategy implementation. This indicated a moderate level of agreement by the respondents.

The results also showed that 81.4% of the respondents either agreed or strongly agreed that frequent communication is a major method to reach shared perceptions, values and beliefs among the workforce and eventually reach a stage of higher performance of the organization. This is an indicator that there was a high level of agreement amongst the respondents which was supported by the high mean score of 4.4068. The standard deviations of all the statements ranged between 0.72256 and 1.11750 indicating that there was little variation between each response and the average response.

Table 4.1(a): Descriptive Statistics of Strategic Communication on Performance of SACCOS

Statements on Strategic Communication	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	Mean	Std. Deviation
Communication plays an important role in determining whether an organization succeeds or not.	0.0%	0.0%	13.6%	28.8%	57.6%	4.4407	0.72256
Communication is deeply connected with strategic consensus and everybody in the organization must know the direction the organization is going and what are the objectives as well they must know the vision, thus the ideal state.	0.0%	22.9%	23.7%	32.2%	21.2%	3.5169	1.06805
The vision of the county is well communicated to the staffs of the organization	0.0%	16.9%	0.0%	16.2%	66.9%	4.3305	1.11750
The firm both the formal and informal forms of communication in strategy implementation	0.0%	37.3%	5.9%	44.9%	11.9%	3.3136	1.09933
Frequent communication is a major method to reach shared perceptions, values and beliefs among the workforce and eventually reach a stage of higher performance of the organization	5.9%	0.0%	12.7%	10.2%	71.2%	4.4068	1.10351

4.1 Inferential Statistics

4.1.1 Pearson Correlation Coefficient Analysis

The Pearson correlation coefficients of this study are illustrated in Table 4.1(b) According to the results, the four independent variables, strategy communication had positive correlations of $r = 0.777$, respectively with the dependent variable, performance of SACCOS in deposits in Kiambu County. Thus, a change in strategy communication by one unit will lead to a 0.777 change in performance of SACCOS in deposits in Kiambu County.

Further, an assessment of the p-values showed that all the independent variables had p-values that were below 0.05 indicating that there is a statistically significant relationship between all of them and the dependent variable. This affirmed

that in instances where there are confidence intervals of 95%, p-values are supposed to be below 0.05 so that the observed differences between groups are not likely to be down to chance and, as such, statistically significant as shown on table 4.1 below.

Table 4.1(b)1: Pearson Correlation Coefficients

		Strategic communication	Performance of SACCOS
Strategic communication	Pearson Correlation	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)		
	N	80	
performance of SACCOS	Pearson Correlation	.777	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	
	N	80	80

4.1.2 Multiple Regression Analysis

Regression is a statistical technique that deals with the determination of linkages between one or more independent variables and a dependent variable by fitting a line of best fit through a series of observations (Mooi & Startstedt, 2014). The summary of the study's multiple regression model is presented in Table 4.2. These results show that the R Square value for all the variables was 0.714 indicating that the model explained 71.4% of any changes in the dependent variable, performance of SACCOS in deposits in Kiambu County whenever there is a one percent change in the independent variables. This means that the model managed to reach the 0.7 threshold for significance of the R Square value as recommended by Hamilton, Ghert and Simpson (2015). This demonstrates a fairly strong goodness-of-fit of the regression model.

Table 4.2: Regression Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.848 ^a	.714	.682	.32978

a. Predictors: (Constant), Strategy Communication

4.1.3 Analysis of Variance

Sawyer (2009) affirmed that the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) is a statistical procedure that attempts to find out existing differences between experimental group means in situations where there are one or more independent variables and a dependent variable. The results of the ANOVA of the study are presented in Table 4.3. The results indicate that the ANOVA F-test score, calculated value F_{cal} at 5% level of significance is equivalent to 21.825, which is greater than the F critical value (F_{crit}) of 2.45 indicating that there is a significant relationship between all the independent variable and the dependent variable of performance of SACCOS. The p-value of 0.000 is less than 0.05 indicating that there is a statistically significant relationship between each of the independent variables and performance of SACCOS in deposits in Kiambu County in accordance with the recommendations of Kao and Green (2008). This demonstrates the goodness of fit of the model.

Table 4.2: Analysis of Variance (ANOVA^a)

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	11.794	1	2.621	21.825	.000 ^b
Residual	26.275	79	.123		
1 Total	37.057	80			

a. Dependent Variable: Performance of SACCOS in deposits in Kiambu County

b. Predictors: (Constant), Strategy Communication

4.1.4 Beta Coefficient Analysis

Beta Coefficients as unknown constants that are projected from the data which are connected to particular independent variables (Peterson & Brown, 2005). These coefficients enable the measurement of the size of change in an independent variable and the manner in which this affects the dependent variable when the rest of the independent variables are held constant. The results of the Beta Coefficients of the study variables are shown in Table 4.4. The values of the constants and coefficients enabled the generation of the following multiple regression model:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \varepsilon$$

$$= 4.311 + 0.572$$

Where, Y refers to the dependent variable (performance of SACCOS), X_1 refers to the strategic communication variable.

According to the equation, taking all the independent variables to be zero, performance of SACCOS will be a constant equivalent to 4.311. A review of the findings also shows that a unit increase in strategic communication will lead to a 0.154 increase in performance of SACCOS when all other independent variables are held constant. Lastly, the p-values for all the variables are all below 0.05, which indicates that they are all statistically significant.

Table 4.4: Beta Coefficients

Coefficients ^a		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
Model		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
	(Constant)	4.311	.582		7.231	.000
1	Strategic communication	.154	.084	.142	1.547	.000

a. Dependent Variable: performance of SACCOS

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

In conclusion basing on the study findings, the study came up with the following conclusions that a unit increase in strategic communication will lead to a 0.154 increase in performance of SACCOS when all other independent variables are held constant. Lastly, the p-values for all the variables are all below 0.05, which indicates that they are all statistically significant.

Basing on the conclusions, the study recommended that the SACCOS management should put into consideration effective communication as it plays an important role in determining whether an organization succeeds or not and that most of the respondents were in agreement with it. Communication is deeply connected with strategic consensus and everybody in the organization must know the direction the organization is going and what are the objectives as well they must know the vision, thus the ideal state. The vision of the county should be well communicated to the staffs of the organization in either formal or informal forms of communication in strategy implementation.

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